

1. Why Dewey decimal classification 16th edition call phoenix schedules?

The "Phoenix Schedules" in the 16th edition of the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) system refer to a revised version of the DDC's schedules that were introduced during the 1990s, primarily in the 16th edition of the classification.

The term "Phoenix" was used metaphorically because, like the mythological phoenix bird, the Dewey Decimal Classification was undergoing a "rebirth" or major transformation. The system was updated significantly, especially in how it handled new and emerging topics, and in reorganizing some areas to improve clarity and ease of use.

The 16th edition was particularly focused on adapting the system to better handle contemporary subjects like technology, environmental issues, and global concerns, reflecting changes in scholarship, culture, and information needs. The use of the term "Phoenix" thus signifies the DDC's revival and modernization, adapting it to a new age of knowledge classification.

It was a major revision aimed at providing better organization and expanding the system's ability to classify modern knowledge.

2. Why is Dewey decimal classification index called the relative index?

The Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) index is called the "relative index" because it provides a way to find subjects and topics based on their relationship to one another within the classification system. Unlike a traditional alphabetical index, which simply lists terms and their corresponding locations, the relative index in the DDC connects related concepts and shows where they fit within the broader structure of the system.

In the relative index:

1. Concepts are organized according to their classification: Instead of listing terms purely alphabetically, the index reflects the Dewey Decimal System's hierarchical structure. This means that related topics are grouped together based on their subject, making it easier to find relevant material within the context of a particular field of knowledge.

2. Cross-referencing: The relative index helps users find specific topics by indicating their number, but it also shows related or similar subjects that might be classified elsewhere, offering a broader understanding of how different ideas are connected.

In short, the "relative" aspect refers to the system's focus on showing the relationships between different subjects and how they are interrelated within the overall classification framework.